

ATTITUDE TOWARDS SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL AWARENESS OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Education

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of the study is to find out the significant relationship between attitude towards social media and Social awareness of Higher Secondary students. The investigator has randomly selected 300 higher secondary students from the randomly selected 10 schools of Sankarankovil taluk for the present study. The sampling technique used in random sampling method. The investigator used survey method of research to correlate attitude towards social media and Social awareness of higher Secondary students. The investigator used attitude towards social media scale (2016) and Social awareness scale (2011). The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyze the correlation between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students. From the result of correlation analysis, it was found that there is no significant relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

KEYWORDS:

social media, social awareness, correlation, attitude, random sampling

INTRODUCTION

In defining cultural and social identity as an integral part of one's self we follow group process are a basic process of self-Perception and social interaction, not merely social behavior, hence" interdependent individuals form a social-psychological system, which transforms qualitatively their character as individuals and gives rise to 'supra-individual'. Social awareness has its roots in the second wave of the feminist movement. It is viewed as one of the key components of consciousness-raising, the other being social action. For many researchers. Awareness about issues affecting the community or raising social consciousness has always been a precursor to social movement. The aims of the public opinion research were to provide the 21st Century Social Work Review Group with a deeper understanding of public knowledge of and attitudes towards, social workers and social work services, and the context in which operate.

Predisposition or a tendency to respond positively or negatively towards a certain idea, object, person or situation. Attitude influences an individual's choice of action, and responses to challenges, incentives, and rewards (together called stimuli). Four major components of attitude are (1) Affective: emotions or feelings. (2) Cognitive: belief or opinions held consciously, (3) Cognitive: inclination for action. (4) Evaluative: positive or negative response to stimuli.

Media are the different types of useful materials, devices and symbols that make the study of a subject more comprehensive and interesting. Media have come to play a fundamental role in modern society. The media of communication –newspaper, magazines, television, radio, movies, computer, movies, videos, CDs and other forms that reach mass audiences.

Social media is the collective of online communications channels dedicated to community-based input, interaction, content-sharing and collaboration. Websites and applications dedicated to forums, micro blogging, social networking. Social book marketing and wikis are among the different types of social media. Social media are computer-mediated tools that allow people to create, share or exchange information, ideas, and pictures/videos in virtual communities and networks. Social media is defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of web2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of user generated content. Furthermore, social media depend on mobile and web-based technologies to create highly interactive platforms through which individuals and communities share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The social media has got a vital role in molding a good society to develop our lifestyle and move it on the right path, because it always try to side with the truth and relevant factor. It is the best tool to spread

awareness in the modern society either it be political, social or economic and giving us latest sight about what is happening in our world, making us aware about our rights, creating awareness against evils in our society, what new happening around us, exposing corrupt politicians and hardcore criminals by sting operations. There is correlation between media and society to share them self about the past, present and future event on need base method of the society. We know that a long time ago we see all news, views events all these things through Radio, Banner and Cinema slide show. But now a day we have a power to see everything of the society and to share it among the people only the good approach of media. So Media and their function have been changed as because there is a competition among the Media also. Therefore apart from the service to the society they have to earn also. From this point of view several media are taking different steps to expand their business and sometimes they are deviated from the principles for which they are functioning. What society will decide for their existences and functioning is mainly depend upon the Govt. rules and regulations by limiting their scope of works in a particular field. In my opinion several sensitive international issues should not be published through Media for which tension among them increased. Otherwise media should come in front of the society with all truth. So social media provide social awareness to the society. With this background the investigator wants to study the attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To find out the significant relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

POPULATION

Population is any group of individuals that have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher. In the present study, the investigator has selected all the higher secondary students who are studying in the schools of Sankarankovil taluk.

SAMPLE

It comprise of a small proportion of individuals, items or events selected for the study from a larger group referred to as a population. By observing the characteristics of the sample, inference can be made about the characteristics of the entire population from which it is drawn. A small portion of population selected for observation is called a sample. The investigator has randomly selected 300 higher secondary students from the randomly selected 10 schools of Sankarankovil taluk for the present study. The sampling technique used in random sampling method.

TOOLS USED

Attitude towards social media scale

It was prepared and validated by Mr. M. Karthick and Dr. N. Subramanian (2016). It is meant for the higher secondary students and important considerations and procedures followed in the construction

of the tool.

Social awareness scale

This scale was developed and standardized by Mahalakshmi and Prabavathyammalpathi (2011).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation for analyse the correlation between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

H0 1: There is no significant relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

Table – 1 Pearson correlation analysis showing the relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students

Correlation	Calculated value of “r”	N	Table of value “r”	Remarks At 5% level
Attitude towards social media and social awareness	0.067	300	0.113	S

It is inferred from the above table that the -value (0.067) is less than the calculated value for df (298) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is no significant relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students.

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

From the result of correlation analysis, it was found that there is no significant relationship between attitude towards social media and social awareness of higher secondary students. It clearly shows that the attitude of higher secondary students does not influence the social awareness of higher secondary students. It may be due to the fact that the school students use mobiles and internet for recreation purpose only.

CONCLUSION

One of the goals of education is social awareness a better understanding of society and the knowledge of available alternatives. The notion of development usually linked to education should, according to Amartya Sen, promise different kinds of freedoms including the freedom of choice. A prerequisite to this freedom is awareness of the alternatives and a sceptical attitude to that which is taken for granted. 'Social awareness' on the other hand, is a conscious process of seeking information about what is happening around us. It is a model whereby one gains fundamental knowledge and information on social issues which encompasses the political, economical, technological, scientific and environmental issues etc. Social awareness is a process of learning and understanding the dynamics of social relationships between individuals, groups and communities. Social media is expanding its reach in every strata of the society in India day by day and today in 2016, we have 195.16 million users of Facebook. In recent years social media has also become a medium to mobilize people for a cause and several social awareness campaigns run by NGO and brands as part of their social corporate responsibility leveraged social media to spread the word. But the student community in India using social media as for recreation purpose. A socially aware individual gives due importance to the rights of citizens and acknowledges the necessity of harmonious social interaction for the developmental progress of the society at large. The role of social media in creating social awareness among the students community may be satisfactory. But the usage of social media by student community exclusively for creating social awareness may not be satisfactory. So the parents and school teachers can motivate their children to use social media for sharing, spreading and understanding the issues related to social activities and due to this, the children may get social awareness.. Not only in sharing the societal activities but also motivate their children to involve in social service.

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